

Dynamic Analysis and Optimization of Intersatellite Links Antennas Specifications in Federated and Fractionated Satellite Systems

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Abstract—While optical InterSatellite Links (ISLs) have gained prominence in emerging telecommunication constellations, they may not be suitable for every mission due to their alignment requirements and system complexity. Alternatively, radiofrequency (RF) ISLs present less stringent requirements but impose limitations on data rates. In this paper, we present a comprehensive dynamic study of ISLs in multiple cases of Federated and Fractionated Satellite Systems (FFSS). Additionally, we examine relay ISL satellite architectures with the goal of achieving optimal link budgets. We uncover distinctive geometrical trajectory characteristics in equialtitude scenarios, which can be exploited to relax antenna steering constraints and facilitating design. A trade-off has been identified that enables the usage of V-Band RF ISLs to achieve Gigabits-per-second (Gbps) data rates while maintaining a reasonably simple RF ISL architecture. The outcomes of this study, that includes complete antenna specifications, have the potential to unlock simplified and accelerated RF ISL design for various types of multi-satellite systems, all at a reasonable cost.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the trend in telecommunication satellites has been to lower the orbit from Geostationary to Low Earth Orbit, aiming to reduce communication delay and increase data rates with ground users. However, this change in orbit came at the cost of varying coverage, leading to the need for more flexible satellite antenna systems. Array antennas are seen as a promising technology allowing higher data rates and more flexibility to provide service to the ground. Unfortunately, array antennas are usually complex and costly due to the necessity of beamforming architectures that, ultimately, limit the size of the antenna. This is one of the challenges that FFSS is tackling [1]. Indeed,

FFSS has emerged as a novel approach to distribute satellite functions across multiple smaller satellites, fostering complementarity between them. In direct-to-cell constellation, FFSS allows to distribute the array antennas over multiple satellites, virtually increasing its surface and, consequently, reducing the beamwidth of the radiation pattern, allowing better selectivity [2]. However, this paradigm shift presents new challenges, particularly the need for independent communication among satellite systems, unbound by ground segment constraints. Intersatellite links have thus become crucial components in FFSS [1]. Despite thorough analysis of ISLs [3], the dynamic behaviour of such links is often overlooked. Optical ISLs is often proposed as the future of telecommunication constellations as it allows data rates of hundreds of Gbps. However, such data rates are not always necessary and implementing optical ISLs brings its own set of limitations. Indeed, challenges such as alignment requirements in the order of the milliradian [4] and system complexity to fit them in the existing electronics and RF architectures on board, could prevent their usage in some missions. On the other hand, RF ISLs provides much wider beamwidth allowing a less sensitive alignment, to the cost of lower gain and thus, usually lower data rate [4].

In this paper, we perform an in-depth study of the ISLs based on a direct-to-cell FFSS use case. The rest of the paper is organised as follows. Section II unravels the orbital mechanic properties of ISLs thanks to orbital simulation and discusses its consequences on antenna specifications. Section III discusses a transparent analog and a transparent digital RF architecture pointing at their limitations and identifying a solution leading to multiple Gbps of data rate. Finally, Section IV draws the conclusions of this study.

II. DYNAMIC ANALYSIS

A. Satellites configuration and analysis

The use case chosen in this analysis is a FFSS with a set of seven satellites but the method presented is applicable to any Satellite System Architecture. The FFSS is composed of one main satellite surrounded by 6 secondaries, located at 600km altitude and with an orbit inclination of 53° . The other orbital elements of the satellites are chosen to create a hexagonal shape. The secondary satellites are distant by 1000km as illustrated in Fig.1. The secondaries will simply act as relays and will not demodulate received data. Each satellite will have a Direct Radiating Array (DRA) of 128 elements and transmit the data stream to the main satellite which will reconstruct the signal. The study has also been performed on the same architecture but with inter-satellite distances of 100km, 10km and 1km; in the rest of the paper, these architectures will only be mentioned when significant differences are noticed.

Orbital simulation has been performed using a Thales Alenia Space, MatLab-based program and all the results have been corroborated by NASA's simulation software GMAT and some by Ansys STK as a validation for the in-house program. The program simulates the orbital behaviour of this set of satellites by propagating their orbits around the earth. In order to correctly interpret the results of the simulations the $u-v$ projection used in this study is normal to the velocity vector of the satellite instead of the satellite to ground vector. However, this projection will be more relevant from a perspective of ISL antenna design. A representation of the position of this plane is shown in Fig.2.

Fig. 1: Example of a fractionated satellite system.

Fig. 2: Position of the projection plane with respect to the satellite.

The advantage of this projection lies in centering the relative behaviour of the secondary satellites on the projection. Indeed, in the usual projection, the secondary satellites are located at the edges of the plot, which would make their movement difficult to interpret. The behaviour of a set of satellites at an equialtitude can be split in 4 phases:

- Equatorial phase: All the satellites are near the equator, they are at their most spread out configuration, the distance between them is maximal.

- Gathering phase: They move on their respective orbits toward the poles, the satellites will get closer until they cross.
- Polar phase: They are located around the nearest point on their orbit to the pole, they are in the configuration where they are the closest, they look almost aligned.
- Spreading phase: They are now spreading out while moving from the pole to the equator.

Each phase occurs twice per orbital period and are depicted in Fig.3.

Fig. 3: Illustrations of the different phases of a fractionated satellite system

B. Crescent Trajectory

Projecting the position of the secondary satellites on the plane shown in Fig. 2 helps better grasp the regularity of their relative movements:

Fig. 4 shows the trace of all the positions of the three satellites located in front of the main one. We can observe two distinct type of traces:

One satellite is static at $u = 0$ and $v = -0.07$ which correspond to about -5° . This satellite is the satellite located on the same orbit and is static with respect to the center one.

The two other traces are superimposed and describe a "crescent" pattern. They vary from $u = -0.86$ to $u = 0.86$ which correspond to $\pm 60^\circ$ and from $v = -0.035$ to $v = -0.075$ which correspond to -2° and -5° respectively. Note that the four phases described above are organised on the $u-v$ plot as: first, the equatorial phase on the edge of the plot ($u = \pm 0.86$), second,

Fig. 4: Location and trajectory of the three front-side satellite

gathering phase until reaching the center ($u = 0$), third, the polar phase at the center, finally the spreading phase from the center to the other edge of the plot. The sharp variations at the edges of the plot is due to a remnant of numerical calculation and does not have any physical significance.

This shows that a group of satellites will have a limited range of relative motion between each other as long as they are in an equalaltitude configuration. The range of motion on the v axis (3°) is here calculated with a distance between satellites of 1000km at the equator (the farthest distance on their orbits). Simulation have also been performed at 100km, 10km and 1km; they respectively show a range of angles on the v axis of 0.3° , 0.03° and 0.003° .

We would like to underline the importance of this results by adding that this range of angles can be smaller than the beamwidth of the RF antenna. On the other hand, the range of angles in the u axis stays constant with the distance ($\pm 60^\circ$). The consequence of this result will be discussed in Section II-C.

Additionally, the four phases described earlier are not equally long. Indeed, the equatorial phase is much longer than the polar phase, this can be seen in the representation of the percentage of time spent in a specific area of the $u-v$ plot. Fig.5 shows the percentage of time spent by one of the satellite over the course of the "crescent" pattern. The brightest spots in Fig.5 correspond to the most time spent in these areas. As can be seen on the bar plot at the top of the Fig.5 the satellite is located between $u = -0.9$ and $u = -0.7$ and, symmetrically, between $u = 0.7$ and $u = 0.9$ for more than 30% of the time. The bar plot on the right show similar information but for the v axis, the satellite will be located below $v = -0.055$ about 50% of the time.

These results can be used in order to optimize the performance of the ISL link in these zones as they are the longest and stablest.

This "crescent" pattern always occurs in an equalaltitude configuration. Adding satellites at different orbital parameters will change the ranges in u and v but not the existence of this pattern. For instance, if the targeted

satellite are further away, the average v axis will be further from 0 and the range will change but the pattern will remain. However, this pattern disappears in a non equalaltitude configuration as the satellites will not move at the same speed.

C. Discussion on Beamwidth

In this section, we discuss the consequences of the previous findings. For the discussion, we will consider 4 possible requirements and draw the associated antenna specifications.

A first possibility is relevant if the system requires permanent line of sight with the targeted satellites. In this case, the ISL antenna should cover the whole range of u and v previously described. For 1000km this means 3° in v and 120° in u . Using the approximation (2.27) of [5]:

$$D_0 \approx \frac{41253}{\Theta_{1d}\Theta_{2d}} \quad (1)$$

with Θ_{1d} and Θ_{2d} the half power beamwidth (HPBW) respectively in the vertical and horizontal plane, the directivity of a beam with 3° in v and 120° in u is $20.6dB$. For 100km the v beamwidth becomes 0.3° and the directivity $30.6dB$.

A second possibility is to optimise the beam coverage on the hot spots that represent 30% of the time. In this case the data transfer will be maximised on the hot spots but will be interrupted as targeted satellite exit the beam coverage. This is shown as Beam 1 in Fig.5. Such a beam would be fixed and have a HPBW of about 2° in v and about 20° in u which correspond to a directivity of about $30dB$. A third possibility is if steering capabilities can be implemented. An elegant solution to maximise the directivity while limiting the steering complexity is to make a one dimensional steering along the u axis and having a fixed beam in v . This case, shown as Beam 2 in Fig.5 can have an arbitrarily small HPBW in u and needs to cover the whole range in v . An example of such beam could be 3° in both u and v which corresponds to a directivity of about $36.6dB$.

Finally, for the last possibility, the focus of the system is on maximising data rate and not limiting steering complexity. In this case it might be advantageous to maximise the gain by providing an arbitrarily narrow beam that follows the targeted satellite. This could be done with two dimensional steering or a one dimensional steering following the "crescent" instead of a straight line. This case is depicted as Beam 3 in Fig.5.

One point not discussed before is the attitude accuracy of the satellite. Indeed this can be a limitation as the satellite might rotate thus leading to the degradation of line of sight with the targeted satellites. This inaccuracy is limited as some previous study have found that 0.1° in pointing accuracy is reachable [6][7].

Fig. 5: Percentage of time spent by one satellite at each location. In green, red and yellow the Beam 1, Beam 2 and Beam 3 respectively.

III. ARCHITECTURE

A. Internal RF architecture

To optimize the ISL and predict the required data rate, we need to take into account the RF ISL architecture used in the satellites. This architecture is strongly linked to the requirements of the mission and cannot be generalised. In our calculation a Direct Radiating Array (DRA) of 128 radiating elements was used in order to model a realistic system. As our goal is the simplification of the satellites, we will use relay architectures. The first, simplest, architecture we considered is known as a "bent pipe" and details of the concept are available in [8]. The architecture aims at concatenating the received band from each radiating element from the user antenna to the ISL frequency band, see Fig. 6.

Fig. 6: Bent pipe concept

The concept shown in Fig. 6 has three main steps:

- 1) Receive the user signal on each radiating elements (RE).
- 2) Filter and transpose the signal to different sections of the ISL band.
- 3) Combine the different sections, filter, and send them with the ISL antenna.

The challenge in this concept lies in minimizing losses along the RF chain as well as avoiding interference between the radiating elements signals. Unfortunately, in the use case studied, 128 radiating elements implies to fit 128 times the 15MHz user band in the 12GHz bands which leads to a very narrow bands filtering ($15MHz/12GHz = 0.00125\%$). Such demanding filtering response is not feasible with the current technologies [9]. Additionally, this architectures requires a different upconversion for each radiating element, thus leading to an unrealistic number of 128 different local oscillators.

These considerations lead us to choose a digital architecture, better suited for our use case, see Fig.7. This architecture requires processing capabilities on board but is almost insensitive to noise.

Fig. 7: Secondary satellite architecture

The goal of this architecture is to digitalise the bandwidth received and transmit it to the main satellite with the ISL band. To do so, first, the user signal is received on each radiating element. Second, the signals are filtered and amplified. Third they are down converted to the baseband for the digitalisation.

Then comes the digitalisation of the signal that requires the sampling and quantisation of the information. For the sampling, assuming a classical S-Band direct to cell satellite, the band to digitalise would be 15MHz. The sampling frequency must be at least twice this bandwidth, we decided to select a bandguard of 20% leading the sampling frequency to $f_s = 36MHz$. As digital data is transmitted, an overhead in the dataframe is required, we chose here an overhead of 8%. This has for a consequence that the ISL data rate would be :

$$R_{ISL} = f_s \times (1 + overhead) \times N_{RE} \times N_{bits} \quad (2)$$

with N_{RE} the number of radiating elements in the DRA and N_{bits} the number of bits.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} R_{ISL} &= 36MHz \times (1 + 0.08) \times 128 \times N_{bits} \\ &= 4976.64 \times 10^6 \times N_{bits} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) shows that the ISL data rate is proportional to the number of bits to digitalise N_{bits} . For each bit added for the digitalisation, the data rate to transmit increase by 5Gbps. Consequently, a trade-off between the quantisation noise error and the data rate needs to be performed. To find this trade-off, an evaluation of the

achievable ISL data rate has been performed.

As a first approximation to find the quantisation noise, we can assume a uniform distribution of the signal, which lead to ((2.12) of [10]):

$$SNR_q = 6.02 \times N_{bits} + 1.76 \text{ (in dB)} \quad (4)$$

For 4 bits it is 25.8dB. This value is way above the SNR that our antenna will receive that we evaluate below 10dB. In other words the quantisation noise is here negligible.

With 4 bits of quantisation, the ISL data rate is brought to almost 20Gbps (3).

B. Modulation

Knowing that we need to transfer 20Gbps over the ISL we can now design the link and modulation required. To do so we first need to channelise the ISL band. To maximise data rate as well as minimise the antenna size, the ISL V-Band that provides 12GHz has been chosen [11]. Modulating the signal over the 12GHz directly is technically unrealistic. Consequently, we decided to split these 12GHz in 6 subbands, each one of them with 10% bandguard for the modulation. This leads to a total of 6, 1.8GHz wide, carriers. We decided not to reuse the polarisation as we consider it being used for the reception instead of the emission. We split the 20Gbps over the carriers, leading to a data rate of roughly 3.4Gbps per carrier. The data rate is $R_{ISL} = \eta * BW_c$ with η the spectral efficiency and BW_c the bandwidth of the carrier. The required spectral efficiency to reach 3.4Gbps is, thus, 1.9bit/s/Hz. Using the DVB-S2X as a reference, this spectral efficiency of 1.9b/s/Hz corresponds to a reasonable 8PSK-25/36 modulation, and the associated SNR_{ISL} is 8dB (see table20a of [12]).

C. Link Budget

Note that the antenna gain are considered equal at the transmitter and receiver. We can determine the power to noise density required $\frac{C}{N_0}$:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{C}{N_0} &= SNR_{ISL} \times BW_{ISL} \text{ in dB} \\ &= 8 + 10 \times \log_{10}(1.8 \times 10^9) \\ &= 100.55 \text{ dBHz} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5)$$

The link budget is performed the same way as in [3], a list of the variables used in the link budget is shown in Table I.

As seen in the Table I, to reach the required data rate at 1000km distance between satellites, a gain of 45.5dB is required at 1W per carrier which seems unreasonable. However, for shorter distances, 100km, 10km and 1km the required gain decreases respectively to 35.5dB, 25.5dB and 15.5dB which are much more reasonable.

TABLE I: Link Budget

Variables	Unit	Value
Carrier frequency	GHz	65
Transmission		
Power	W	1
	dBm	30
Tx losses	dB	1
Tx antenna gain	dBi	45.5
EIRP	dBm	74.5
Propagation		
Distance inter sat	km	1000
Free space losses	dB	188.7
Atmospheric losses	dB	0
Polarization losses	dB	0
Reception		
Received power at the antenna	dBm	-114.2
Rx antenna gain	dBi	45.5
Rx antenna losses	dB	1
Antenna temperature	K	100
Rx noise figure	dB	3
Reference temperature	K	380
System noise temperature	K	478.2
Demodulation losses	dB	1.5
G/T	dB/K	18.7
Other losses	dB	0
C/N0	dBHz	100.6

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we performed a deep analysis of intersatellite links, with dynamic orbital simulation in a Federated and Fractionated Satellite System. We uncovered a "crescent" pattern in the ISL dynamic behaviour in an equialtitude scenario. This pattern could simplify the antenna design by reducing the steering requirements to a one dimensional one, while variation in the other dimension can be absorbed by the antenna beamwidth. We performed a preliminary design of a Radio Frequency Architecture for a relay ISL. This lead to the identification of limitations in the data rate at large distances but underline the potential realisation of nearly 20Gbps ISL at less than 100km distance. Further work could be performed to include more architectures.

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